

The Two Cinderellas: Prospection and Evaluative Cohesion.

From Discourse Organisation to Corpora and Back Again

Tread softly because you tread on my dreams

(W.B. Yeats)

we gain clarity, wisdom, and understanding of our life's narrative only by looking back in hindsight, yet we are forced to live in the present, moving forward into an uncertain future

(S. Kierkegaard)

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Abstract

Evaluative cohesion is the long-overlooked counterpart to propositional cohesion in discourse. While the latter has been extensively theorised within systemic-functional and text-linguistic traditions, the former remains comparatively under-described, despite its central role in how texts are interpreted and experienced.

This paper argues that evaluative cohesion is intrinsically linked to a further, almost equally under-theorised dimension of discourse organisation: Sinclairian *prospection*, or the forward-oriented projection of expectations. Discourse unfolds not through backward-looking (anaphoric) links, but principally through the continuous anticipation of what is to come. These expectations are not neutral: they are evaluatively charged, guiding the reader or listener towards particular interpretations and responses.

The central claim advanced here is that texts must cohere not only propositionally but evaluatively. Where evaluative expectations are disrupted without resolution, discourse risks incoherence, regardless of its propositional well-formedness. Prospection, in this

sense, is the principal temporal (speech) / spatial (writing) mechanism through which evaluative cohesion is established and maintained.

I will illustrate this through a series of examples - from poetry, political discourse and even popular song - showing how expectations are built, maintained, and sometimes deliberately disrupted for effect.

I will then briefly show how corpus evidence allows us to move beyond individual texts to recurring patterns and, finally, suggest that what we are dealing with here is not a marginal phenomenon, but a central organising principle of discourse — one that, interestingly, is now being operationalised at scale by Large Language Models.

In short, the two claims are simple: discourse coheres evaluatively as well as propositionally and it does not just proceed — it projects and anticipates, and not just syntactically, but also semantically and evaluatively.

1 The theoretical challenges

1.1 Two traditional focuses

First, corpus discourse studies has traditionally emphasised retrospective patterning, in particular anaphoric referencing (from Halliday and Hasan 1976 to Hoey 2017) i.e. that meaning emerges from previous co-text, and the job of the discourse analyst is to look back to discover how the current utterance has acquired its meaning. Even in the most complex accounts of the grammar of reference and cohesion (coherence), such as Halliday & Matthiessen 2004 [2014], anaphora (Gr. backward-bearing), is given full attention, for instance:

- pronouns; demonstratives (this, here, now);
- ellipsis: ‘How old is he?’ ‘Three months’
- substitution: ‘Now you can't just blame this on imperialism, though many people have tried to do so’ (Ferguson TED talk, 2011)

While cataphora: (Gr. forward-bearing) reference is treated in just two paragraphs, just the simple mirror of anaphora (pronouns, demonstratives).

However, as Sinclair argues (1990/2004) the cataphoric or prospective (Lat. ‘forward-looking’) dimension to discourse studies is unjustly much neglected. Discourse building as well as discourse interpreting also works prospectively: lexical priming (both general and local recent, intertextual priming) cataphorically activates expectations. Semantic, including evaluative, frames are set up in advance and as we proceed through a discourse. Text/texts are ‘finished product’, stabilised, available for analysis (including by CL means, phenomena are countable) and for (diverse) interpretation. Discourse is meaning in the making, driven forward by decisions being made, primings being enacted, a strategy yet to be completed, not yet stabilised and where both speaker and listener prospection is paramount.

I am using ‘evaluation’ in the sense thoroughly well-described in Thompson and Hunston (2000), Hunston (2004 *et passim*) of the indication that something is good or bad, with goodness and badness coming in an infinite variety of different guises. It is argued here that evaluation is an animal instinct vital for survival, we evaluate as we breathe, and therefore unsurprisingly – but in the past oddly unnoticeably – it pervades all language at every level from lexis to text. We can even add that, all too often evaluation *precedes* understanding, we frequently evaluate first than call that ‘understanding’.

Prospection guides interpretation, as Sinclair (2004) stresses we generally do not need to anaphorically (Gr, ‘backward-carrying’) flick back through pages, we are too busy working out what is about to come, how the discourse will wind up and how cohesive overall it will be. Prospection is the true driving force of discourse.

Of course readers will note that much referencing is *both* backward- and forward-looking as indeed with ‘the implications are daunting’. Something which has implications has already been mentioned, what the daunting implications are is still to

come. We might call this ‘Janus’ referencing, from the Roman God who famously simultaneously looked back to the past and forward to the future:

Janus: ‘The God of discourse’. Observing the past, constructing the future.

An analysis of the CQL [word="the"] [lemma="implication|effect|consequence"] [lemma="be"] [tag="JJ.*"] confirms that the frame being set is very generally evaluatively negative (as in Sinclair’s example). In the SiBol corpora (available through *Sketch Engine*)¹ we obtain:

The implications are disturbing.

The consequences are severe.

while that of the richer CQL: [word="the"] [lemma="implication|effect|consequence"] [lemma="be"] [tag="R.*"]? [tag="JJ.*"] render:

The implications are incredibly dangerous.

The consequences are potentially disastrous / painfully visible

Although, interestingly, ‘the effects are’ are often positive. Second, evaluative cohesion is the lonely, long-overlooked sibling of the justly much celebrated, and studied notion of propositional cohesion (Halliday and Hasan 1976, Halliday & Matthiessen 2004/2014). If, as in Hoey’s excellent simile ‘ideas are like people. They have direct

¹ <https://www.sketchengine.eu/>

ancestors and share genes with their siblings. [...] they can become surrounded by ideas they have given birth to' (2017, ix), then evaluative cohesion is the Cinderella of discourse analysis, who never even got invited to the Ball. The novelties I wish to propose here are (a) that evaluation functions not just locally but is also a principle of whole-text organisation (as in Problem-Solution, Contrast, Cause and Consequence [as in our first epigraph] and Crescendo) and that (b) in real-life discourse, cataphora is much more varied, complex, engaging, even powerful than is usually described. If anything, it is anaphora who is the poor relation.

1.2 Cinderella and other folk motifs

It is worth spending a moment of the use of the term *Cinderella*, which will crop up again in this paper, perhaps cohesively, certainly evaluatively. A concordance of the item in the SiBol corpus reveals traces of several metonymic extensions of the Cinderella folk-motifs. These include the one activated above:

- 1) The (unjustly) forgotten, neglected entity: ‘mental health, for so long the “Cinderella” of the health service [...]’ (negative)
- 2) Sudden transformation (vast improvement, sometimes wished for) (positive)
‘I know that a Cinderella magic wand is needed in Nigeria’

- 3) Dreams come true (positive) ‘My story is really, really crazy. It is a Cinderella story. Nobody would think I'd play for the national team [...]
- 4) ‘Rags to riches’: Poor girl comes good / gets lucky (including the ‘heart-of-gold’ working-girl movies: *Pretty Woman*, *Irma La Douce* – with heavy doses of euphemism, sometimes called ‘moral hygiene’), generally positive for the women involved. ‘Marriage to a rich and famous man might be the dream of a million Cinderellas [...]

The persistence of the ‘Cinderella’ motif across discourse — denoting neglect, transformation, aspiration, and reversal — itself provides a particularly clear illustration of evaluative cohesion in operation: a shared evaluative schema which is activated, elaborated, and recontextualised across texts.

What, on the other hand, came as a surprise (at least to me) is that there is no evidence of such metonymic extensions of the folk tale in the *Word Sketch of Cinderella*, where co-occurring items such as *Ball*, *slipper*, *godmother*, *Rapunzel*, *pantomime* appear instead.

The same is true of *Frankenstein*. The SiBol concordance reveals traces of the metonymic, clearly evaluatively extension of allegedly ‘bad’ science working against ‘good’ nature’, e.g. ‘Frankenstein science’ / Franken foods’, whereas *Word Sketch* brings up the names of other monsters (*Golem*, *mummies*). The reader might wish to research other similar folk and fictional characters (Pinocchio, Faust, Robin Hood, and characters from non-European cultures) comparing different CL tools.

2. Evaluative cohesion: an example of how we really process texts

The following is the book-blurb of the immensely influential *The Bottom Billion*, written by Paul Collier, expert in international development, which was declared by the UN to be ‘book of the year’ in 2008:

Global poverty is falling rapidly; but in fifty or so failing states the world's poorest people - the "bottom billion"- face a tragedy that is growing inexorably worse. Why do these states defy all attempts to help them? Why does current aid seem unable to make a difference?

In his award-winning bestseller, Paul Collier pinpoints the issues of corruption, political instability, and resource management that lie at the root of the problem, and offers hard-nosed solutions and real hope for a way of solving one of the great crises facing the world today.

The text is meant to be both informative but also persuasive (and so evaluative: buy the book). There are two subjects being evaluated, failing states and Collier's suggested solutions. It would be a simple, automatised and utterly futile activity to simply count up the number of positive items ('attempts to help them', 'hard-nosed solutions', 'real hope') then the negative ones ('poorest people', 'a tragedy', 'corruption', and so on) to calculate whether the subjects are evaluated positively or negatively. For the simple reason that this is not how normally primed readers process texts.

Instead, using the negation first adopted in Morley and Partington (2009) of round brackets signalling positive and square brackets negative evaluation, the reader, primed by experience of similar texts processes the text into three evaluative blocks:

1. (Global poverty is falling rapidly);
2. **but** [in fifty or so failing states the world's poorest people - the 'bottom billion'- face a tragedy that is growing inexorably worse. Why do these states defy all attempts to help them? Why does current aid seem unable to make a difference?
3. (In his award-winning bestseller, Paul Collier pinpoints the issues of corruption, political instability, and resource management that lie at the root of the problem, and offers hard-nosed solutions and real hope for a way of solving one of the great crises facing the world today.)

The reader makes use of two psycholinguistic faculties, ubiquitous in discourse processing. The first is recognising *embedded evaluation*, the first phrase being a perfect example. 'Global poverty' is bad but its 'falling rapidly is good and we read it as a single positive unit ([Global poverty] is falling rapidly), the outer brackets determining the overall evaluation, here bad inside overall good. There are several other examples in the text [defy (attempts to help them)], this time, positive embedded in overall negative.

The second principle is that of *evaluative inertia*, that is, while reading a text we normally carry on processing with the same evaluative polarity until instructed to do otherwise.² Note in the above text the use of the item 'but' as an evaluative switch, signalling that the evaluation is about to change (a function shared by all contrastives, e.g. *however, yet, although, despite*, and so on, all corpus-software searchable items. See Partington (2017) for a fuller explanation.

CL analysis can elucidate a number of 'non-obvious' features of the evaluative work being done in this text. A SiBol corpus concordance of the lexical template *attempts*

² With the very notable exception of the phenomenon of evaluative clash, when items of opposite evaluative polarities are juxtaposed either for effect 'fraught with ... delightful possibilities' or simply by time-pressure mistakes, 'the number of positive-sum games that humans tend to be embroiled in' (Partington 2017).

(or *efforts*) to (help, alleviate, improve – all positive items in themselves) are strongly primed for [failure] and [frustration]:

Mr Cameron's [(attempts to detoxify the Tories' image) have failed] (SiBol 13) including this example on the very subject of international development:

Is it possible that rich nations' [(attempts to help the developing world) only encourage dependency and corruption]? (SiBol 05)

And then 'Paul Collier (pinpoints [the issues of ...])'. The SiBol concordance shows conclusive evidence that it is far better to *pinpoint* than not to, for example, and note the embedding:

Torres says that is down to the manager's ability to (pinpoint his team's [key problem] and address it). (SiBol 13)

Finally, and most germanely to the topic of this paper, our conscious or semiconscious primings inform us that the overall textual organisation of this piece is problem-solution and that it is the very evaluative contrast between problem (negative, frequently, as here, expressed with questions) and solution (positive evaluation, with proffered solutions ('hard-nosed' i.e. realistic, and 'real hope').

3. Textual organisation patterns

The pre-CL work, in particular of Winter (1977) and Hoey (1983, 1991) on which my own work is based (Partington 2025), suggest a number of frequently-employed patterns of organisations of text. These include:

Problem – solution (see Hoey 1994 for a Chapter-length analysis)

Matching pairs (both comparison and contrast)

Cause – effect / consequence

Crescendo

‘Garden Path’

At the level of close reading, these models are sometimes readily identifiable. However, without further corroboration, they risk remaining within the domain of interpretive insight. The contribution of corpus linguistics is precisely to extend such observations beyond the individual text, demonstrating that these patterns are not idiosyncratic, but recurrent and systematically distributed across texts, even across discourse-types.

3.1 Problem – Solution

To the Bottom Billion text analysed above and Hoey’s work we might add that many Q-R discourse-types (from press briefings to internet forums) are often organised and structured whereby a problem (outlined in the question) is prospective of one or more solutions (suggested in the response). Diegoli includes the following exchange from a Japanese on-line forum (her translation):

Q: (2) ‘[Many unpleasant things have been happening one after the other], so I’d like to (focus on just one thing, without thinking about anything else). Please suggest to me (some ways to escape from reality that, like walking, don’t cost money).

R: How about (strength training)? I think (training your body can also stabilise your mind), (make you feel better), and (it’s good for your health). ([As long as you don’t overdo it], it should be fine.)’

(Partington and Diegoli 2026)

The following is from a Chinese Foreign Affairs press briefings (the invitation is a problem, ‘wrongdoing’ for the Chinese administration):

Q: [On the European Parliament’s invitation to the Dalia Lama?]

Podium: (China ... is firmly opposed to [this wrongdoing of the European parliament) [...] [The leaders of the European Parliament have sabotaged China's core interests]. It is hoped that (the EU side and relevant people can correct their wrongdoing and take effective measures to eradicate the negative impact inflicted by their mistake).

And this especially noteworthy exchange is from a White House briefing:

Q: The Associated Press reports that on Sunday in Middlebury, Vermont, where you gave a speech and were given an alumni achievement award, [there were around 500 protestors].

Ari Fleischer: Oh no, (there were more than that). <Laughter>

(from Partington 2006)

The questioner implies that protestors are a problem for the press secretary. His reply rather cleverly ironically reverses the evaluation of numbers of protestors; the more there are the more important I am.

In all Q-R discourse-types, problem-solution text organisation can be researched by looking for lexical signals of 'how?' explanation questions 'how do/ did (you, we, the administration etc.) ...?'.

3.2 Matching pairs

Hoey (2005) includes a passage explicitly contrasting the military skills of Generals Grant and Lee in which those of the former are explicitly evaluated as superior.

The same volume includes two extracts from Bryson humorous travelogue, in which the matching contrasts are especially intricate and fascinating. The first is:

- (1) In winter Hammerfest is a thirty-hour ride by bus from Oslo, though [why anyone would want to go there in winter is a question worth considering]. (2) [It is on the edge of the world], the northernmost town in Europe, as far from

London as London is from Tunis, [a place of dark and brutal winters, where the sun sinks into the Arctic Ocean in November and does not rise again for ten weeks.] (3) (I wanted to see the Northern Lights. (4) Also, I had long harboured a half-formed urge to experience what life was like in such [a remote and forbidding place]). (5) (Sitting at home in England with a glass of whisky and a book of maps, this had seemed a capital idea.)

Simple close reading reveals the contrast between the negative evaluation of the place and the positive evaluation of the author's urges. Concordancing can take us deeper. A concordance of *a place of* in reveals how it systematically right cooccurs with unmistakably evaluative word groups, some literal and more often figurative. In this particular corpus, the evaluation is most likely to be positive, for example *welcome and hope, youthful enchantment, joy and prayer, new beginnings, stunning natural beauty*, with only the occasional negative occurrence, *extreme ignorance, ambiguity and uncertainty*. Bryson's use, then, is not unique but minority in its negativity. Similarly, a concordance of *such a * place*, also shows how it is almost always used to express evaluation (as in Bryson's piece) both positive and negative, e.g. *such a bountiful / amazing / desirable place* but also *worrying / parlous / deplorable place*.

The whole passage continues with more cohesion-creating matching contrasts, both temporal (before – now) and the author's emotions:

(6) [But now as I picked my way through the grey, late-December slush of Oslo I was beginning to have my doubts, (7) Things had not started well. (8) I had overslept at the hotel, missing breakfast, and had to leap into my clothes] [...] (9) We approached Hammerfest from above, on a winding coast road, and when at last it pivoted into view (it looked simply wonderful – a fairyland of golden lights stretching up into the hills and around an expansive bay.) (10) [I had pictured it in my mind as a village – a few houses around a small harbour, a church perhaps, a general store, a bar if I was lucky] – (but this was a little city. (11) A golden little city. (12) Things were looking up.)

(Adapted from Hoey, 2005, p. 126)

Note how the *but* in both sentence (6) and (10) act as evaluation switches. Note too how the first part is cohesively prospective of, anticipates, the second part of the pair (as in *before* ,, *now*).

3.3 Cause – effect / consequence

If many problem-solution structures can be sought by the question ‘how?’, then cause-effect, also known as ‘reason’ structures, as in the epigraph to this paper (speech act of instruction followed by the reason) can be sought by the question ‘why?’ and it’s many searchable signals, for example, *the reason why*, ... *the real reason why*, ... *what happened / went wrong was ... even if ...* (counter-expectational prospection) ... *if you ask me*:

If you ask me, I think that protecting the oil supply may have been part of the reason.

(enTenTen21)

Corpora can be constructed of ‘why’-explanation discourse types which can range from newspaper op-eds, to ‘why-so-sad?’ lost-love songs, also bearing in mind that ‘how’-explanation and ‘why’ explanations often co-exist in the same text.

3.4 Crescendo

‘Crescendo’ (Italian: ‘growing’, ‘increasing’) cohesion is achieved by the discourse piling evaluative lexis of one polarity on top of others of the same polarity. At some point the text receiver expects more of the same and even a climax of some sort. The effect is illustrated by Hoey’s (2005, 173-174) analysis of a text from Dicken’s *Pictures*

from Italy (1846).³ The author, at his most typically contrarianist, plays with the evaluation of ruin, ruined using such startling collocations and phraseology as:

mounds, and heaps, and hills, of **ruin**

but all the way was **ruin**

miles of **ruin**

housed in **ruin**

Climax: [the sun] looked its last, that day, upon **a ruined world**.

And the site of all this frightful ‘ruin’? The Ancient Appian Way outside Rome, a World Heritage Beauty Site. Dickens diligently avoids the plural term *ruins* with its frequent positive evaluation, evident in concordances and *Work Sketch* :

a daydream of lush rainforests, ancient ruins and stunning landscapes

imposing, majestic, exquisitely preserved ruins

(enTenTen21)

4. The symbiosis of prospection and evaluative cohesion: workshopping ‘To His Coy Mistress’

Before the last of the structures of text organisation listed in Section 3 (namely ‘Garden Path’), we might fruitfully examine a text which employs several of the organisational techniques already discussed, namely Andre Marvell’s (1621-78) celebrated short poem ‘To His Coy Mistress’.

³ Available at <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/650/650-h/650-h.htm>

Now therefore, while the youthful hue	
Sits on thy skin like morning dew,	
And while thy willing soul transpires	35
At every pore with instant fires,	
Now let us sport us while we may;	
And now, like am'rous birds of prey,	
Rather at once our time devour,	
Than languish in his slow-chapp'd power.	40
Let us roll all our strength, and all	
Our sweetness, up into one ball;	
And tear our pleasures with rough strife	
Thorough the iron gates of life.	
Thus, though we cannot make our sun	45
Stand still, yet we will make him run.	

We can perform the analysis by asking a number of questions which help highlight the organisation. But before analysing it is important to recall that Marvell was a Yorkshireman from Hull, who almost certainly spoke with a northern English accent (very different from the modern RP ‘mis-recitations’ to be found on various websites) and at a time when spoken English even in England was still almost entirely rhotic, as in modern Scots. Where an ‘r’ is found in the text, it was pronounced as, for instance, ‘world’, ‘Humber’, ‘adore’, ‘thirty’: a major contribution to the poem’s assonance. The items ‘would’, ‘should’, ‘Flood’ and ‘love’ all employ the same vowel (as would ‘Sun’ and ‘run’ in the very final couplet), namely. [u], and ‘our’, ‘devour’ and ‘power’ all end in [aur].

The whole poem is clearly rendered coherent, comprehensible, by its evaluative techniques. The rhyme scheme is in rhyming couplets, fitting to its subject. The first stanza is also organised by *matching pairs*, especially apt in describing his thoughts (‘I’), desires and imagined behaviours compared with those of the object of his love (‘you’), including dramatic contrasts, such as the exotic ‘Indian Ganges’ and the local Hull river, the Humber as well as the immeasurably distant past and equally distant imagined future. The two most obvious objects of evaluation, the lady and his love for her are both evaluated very positively (naturally):

For, lady, you deserve this state,
Nor would I love at lower rate.

The series of positive evaluations help create the cohesion of the stanza. And just as obviously, the positive evaluation is also organisationally in a crescendo form. However, there is a perhaps less obvious object of evaluation, the situation he is in (see below).

The stanza also describes a counterfactual world, introduced by ‘Had we’ with verb-forms introduced by the ‘should’ and ‘would’, underscoring the unreal, the hypothetical. And, in terms of the present essay, it is functionally highly prospective, cataphoric; any experienced listener will expect some kind of future shift from such a counterfactual world to a more possible one.

Counterfactual prospection is a potentially very rich area for corpus-assisted text-organisation research. It has a very wide variety of lexical markers from many versions of ‘if’ (‘what if’, ‘if we were/had’, ‘only if’) through the ‘had we ...’ of this text and to semi-fixed introductory templates such as ‘imagine that’, ‘just think’, ‘Should we/they have ...?’, and so on. In terms of evaluations, hypotheticals most generally imply some sort of problem, something missing, as in this first stanza. His situation is not the ideal one it could be.

The second stanza is indeed just such an abrupt shift. The verb tense is present and very immediate. Clearest of all is the change in evaluation (introduced yet again we notice by ‘But’). The present and future scene outlined is bleak. Marvell’s audience would have recognized it as an instance of the fashionable ‘Memento Mori’ motif ‘Remember that some day you too shall die:

And in terms of this essay's topic, text organisation, we recognise it as 'Problem' negatively evaluation, prospectively anticipating a 'Solution'.

The concordance of 'times wingèd chariot' in enTenTen21 lists 17 occurrences. On three occasions it is used discussing the poem but on the others it is used as a figure for time passing or indeed, simply for being in a hurry:

Sorry to post and run, but **times winged chariot** , etc.

There are also 36 occurrences of another line which has entered into folk memory, 'deserts of vast eternity', 28 of which refer directly to the poem; the others express some variety of negatively evaluated figure of hyperbole:

Now the rug is being pulled on those born between 1960 and 1970, and we have **deserts of vast eternity** to fill before we reach pensionable age and death.

Note too the irony of understatement of the last rhyming couplet of the stanza (see Partington 2006, 2007 and 2011 on using CaDS techniques to research ironic effects).

The third stanza, as prospected, suggests the poet's preferred solution to both the problem explicitly stated in the second, and hinted at in the hypotheticality, namely, the fleeting nature of youth and mortality. It is now or never. And once again the poet employs the Crescendo organisation, building up the tension, the emotion, the urgency.

This brief analysis of a single poem, a short but complete text, has illustrated several of the text organisation patterns listed above; matching pairs, not only 'I' – 'you' but also 'hypothetical' – 'real', problem and preferred solution and two examples of

Crescendo (all three stanzas end with highly evaluative couplets). And, above all, in the context of this essay discourse-building prospection is inextricably bound up with several series of cohesive evaluations, all of which renders the text tightly coherent. Indeed, without taking evaluative cohesion into account, the whole poem makes no sense whatsoever.

Throughout the analysis we also divined that traditional close-reading can be supported, corroborated and augmented by CL searches in the investigation of text organisation (beyond the phrase). A list of simple suggestions of markers might include:

Hypothetical / counterfactual: *Had we...If we had...*

Causal / justificatory: *For, because, since...*

Contrastive / disruption: *But, however, nevertheless, (al)though ... yet ...*

Resolution / directive: *Now therefore...Let us...*

Addition (emphasis) : *moreover, what's more* (revealing evaluative impetus)

5. Prospection as Trickster

We have already discussed how prospection / cataphora is the Cinderella of reference studies, the unjustly neglected sibling. But the plot thickens.

The prospection (and its evaluative modelling) follows, more or less, some form of expectation. Marvell was not the first nor the last to implore his heart's desire and his audience would have recognised the *Carpe Diem* ('gather ye rosebuds while ye may') form. But prospection can also be – notoriously in text-types like a detective or mystery novel – a trickster.

5.1 The 'Garden Path' organisation

The ‘Garden Path’ strategy, from the folk saying to ‘lead down (or up) the garden path’, that is, to lead astray – in its literal form, in order to press one’s amorous suit in seclusion – is a high risk but high reward strategy. In the enTenTen21 corpus, the item ‘down the garden path’ occurs 1731 times and ‘up the garden path’ 152, and there is no doubting its negative evaluation in figurative use:

Having been led down the garden path by promises of "comparative advantage" and the wonders of "free trade," we are now being made painfully aware of the real downsides these policies have created.

But to my scrutiny as least there is little inkling either of why we sometimes allow ourselves to be so *led* (the most commonly left-cooccurring verb), nor that we sometimes enjoy it, nor of its role as rhetorical organisation.

The ‘Garden Path’ speaker/writer begins by outlining an evaluative narrative, most generally one that an audience is familiar with, only to radically upset the storyline pointing with some degree of drama how it is misleading and what the true state of affairs really is (in their view of course). Partington (2025) outlines two TED talks in which the speaker exploits the Garden Path organisation. The first is Harvard Professor Steven Pinker’s ‘The Surprising Decline in Violence’.⁴

https://www.ted.com/talks/steven_pinker_the_surprising_decline_in_violence?language=en

He first shows his audience scenes of 20th Century atrocities and reads newspaper accounts of how idyllic the pre-modern life was before pre-announcing his own contrary thesis:

Now, the original title of this session was, "Everything You Know Is Wrong," and I'm going to present evidence that this particular part of our common understanding is wrong, that, in fact, our ancestors were far more violent than

⁴https://www.ted.com/talks/steven_pinker_the_surprising_decline_in_violence?language=en

we are, that violence has been in decline for long stretches of time, and that today we are probably living in the most peaceful time in our species' existence.

All 'Garden Path' formats must, of necessity, have their more or less dramatic 'moment of revelation' in which the true narrative is revealed. . Here we have the two phrases 'Everything You Know Is Wrong', and 'this particular part of our common understanding is wrong'. Phrases like 'common understanding' and 'generally accepted belief' are often CL searchable signals that 'common belief' is misguided and the speaker's own different, 'accurate' narrative is on the horizon. We might also note he is also using a matching pair of different hypotheses, one evaluated as superior to the other. The rest of this talk contains evidence for the relative historical decline in violence. Wars, public torture and execution were once the norm rather than exceptions, homicide rates have plummeted from as far back as records begin, we no longer burn 'witches'.

At least as controversial a 'Garden Path' is the Chinese-American journalist Leslie Chang's talk entitled 'The Forgotten Voices of Chinese Workers'.

Leslie Chang, author of *Factory Girls: From Village to City in a Changing China*.

She spent a year living alongside young female workers who migrate from rural areas to work in China's big industrial cities as research for her book *Factory Girls: From Village to City in a Changing China*. :

http://www.ted.com/talks/leslie_t_chang_the_voices_of_china_s_workers.html

She begins by creating a matching evaluative contrast between the West and China in which the former are the beneficiaries and the latter the victims of globalisation, and that westerners drive millions of Chinese workers to migrate to the cities and factories and are, therefore, guilty for the suffering of Chinese workers, labelling this ‘simple narrative’ as ‘appealing’ (to a self-indulgently guilt-ridden audience of westerners, like that of a TED-talk).

The shift, indeed reversal, of evaluative narrative could scarcely be more jolting: ‘but it's also inaccurate and disrespectful’ (note how ‘but’ once again signals evaluative about-turn). The young women she had lived alongside had gladly embraced factory life in Eastern China – clearly hardly ideal - in exchange for the grinding poverty and social aridity of rural Western China. Not only is the life of female factory work evaluated anew, Chang’s narrative is now:

They choose to leave their homes in order to earn money, to learn new skills, and to see the world. In the ongoing debate about globalization, what's been missing is the voices of the workers themselves

which Chang then claims to know, through the authority of having spoken to a representative variety of them but so is Chang’s audience ‘we [meaning *you*] must be peculiarly self-obsessed [...]’. She depicts her audience as lazy, ignorant and even quasi-racist, a high-risk strategy indeed.

5.2 Workshopping the ‘Garden Path’ organisation: ‘Human’

‘Human’ is a well-known song (with video) from the 1980s by *The Human League* available at:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s1ysoohV_zA&list=RDs1ysoohV_zA&start_radio=1

while the lyrics alone can be read here:

<https://genius.com/The-human-league-human-lyrics>

The song is in two parts, the first beginning with ‘Come on, baby, dry your eyes’ and ending with ‘Please forgive me’, delivered by a male singer., though with glimpses of the woman he is addressing.

We might first of all ask the Hoey-ian organisational question: what are the cohesive lexical chains (Hoey 1983, 1991, 2017) [indicative of topics]?

These might fall into the following chains: (i) *sad emotion*: ‘tears’, ‘cry’, (emotional) ‘hurt’; (ii) *emptiness*: ‘void’, ‘gone’, ‘space’, (not) ‘hold’; (iii) *fallibility*: ‘human’ (repeated), ‘mistakes’, ‘flesh and blood’. We can imagine that all these evaluative chains, and the appeal for forgiveness are prospective of (iv) ‘repair’, ‘absolution’, ‘renewal’, ‘hold (again)’, ‘love’. But this prospection is well and truly upended as the woman replies:

The tears I cry aren't tears of pain
They're only to hide my guilt and shame
I forgive you, now I ask the same of you
While we were apart, I was human too

We can now ask which prospections were fulfilled and which not. While the prospection of forgiveness is satisfied we are now faced with a whole new lexical chain ‘guilt’, ‘shame’ and ‘human’ and a new unresolved evaluative narrative, namely, she was ‘fallible’ too, and what will his reaction now be (the video ends with him looking downcast and reflective)?

The items ‘flesh and blood’ and the repeated ‘human’ both bear CL analysis. Concordancing the first in enTenTen21 uncovers a number of associated and interrelated evaluative narratives including:

- 1) Kith and kin, of my family, people, ‘culture’ (**positive**), usually ‘own flesh and blood’ but also often [**negative**] betrayal or extra-guilt (‘spying on one’s own flesh and blood’)
- 2) the ‘not divine’, both:
 - a) earthly, worldly (neutral)
 - b) fallen, capable of sin (religious use) [**negative**]
- 3) closely related: capable of error (usually **negative**, but also used as both self-effacement and also aggressive excuse (positive of self ‘no-one could do better’] and negative of the interlocutor [unreasonable])

Somewhat related, the term ‘flesh* out’ expresses positive evaluation in two ways. Firstly in giving form to (‘mere’) theory or ideas (very positive, and frequent)

This stage of the design process involves **fleshing out** sketch concepts in more detail, looking at every aspect from materials to colours, form and style, to potential manufacturing processes that could be best applied.

He enlivened his books and lectures by **fleshing out** characters from Aaron Burr and John Quincy Adams to George W. Bush and even Michael Jordan.

Here we might remember the ‘Cinderella transformation’ motif of sudden change for the better, as a humanised metonym.

The second emphasises something real, true and accurate not artificial or misleading (positive):

Fleshing out the numbers further, the paper emphasised that as of 2019, only \$10.3 billion have been pledged to the GCF. Of this, only \$7.23 billion has been deposited, \$4.60 billion approved and \$0.39 billion actually disbursed.

Meanwhile concordancing of *human* in the SiBol set of corpora reveals an intricate array of both positive evaluations:

- humane,
- human warmth,
- human dignity,
- human connection,
- resourcefulness,

for instance:

If you believe that the actual purpose of politics is to alleviate the suffering of the people, you will have a lot of **human feelings** in you.

but when people live in a respectable atmosphere they behave like **human beings**.

But what it shows is the incredible array of **human resource talents** that are out there on the streets.

But also (much more rarely, another surprise) negative evaluations:

- human weakness
- human error, fallibility
- human failure

for instance:

Here, we are confronted with the **human face of evil**.

What disambiguates in our text is in the first occurrence ‘*only* human’, again witnessed in the SiBol corpora:

When the interview finally aired, Morsi admitted to his interviewer, his ex-adviser Amr Al-Leithy, that he is **only human** and therefore, makes mistakes like everyone else.

It is **only human** to gloat after a prediction is spot on and say "I said so!"

The sense of fallibility is carried onto the second occurrence in our song - ‘I was human too’ (no ‘only’ this time) - a perfect example of how evaluative cohesion is constructed in on-going discourse.

A second surprise, to me at least, was the comparison of the concordance of *human* with its WordSketch, which, as we know, is essentially a concordance trawler and organiser. Both the positive and negative evaluated senses are drowned out in WordSketch by the most frequent collocating items, such as *human being, rights, capital, universal, basic, trafficking*. In other words, some of the subtleties of human text analysis (pardon the pun) of close reading, get lost in the crowd (though it could be argued that other senses are prioritised).

5.3 Workshopping prospection and evaluative cohesion in political discourse ‘We live in turbulent times’

The TED talk delivered by Lord Paddy Ashdown, one time leader of the UK Liberal Democrat Party, and then High Commissioner to Bosnia is a masterclass in prospection:

http://www.ted.com/talks/paddy_ashdown_the_global_power_shift.html

Indeed the only clue in the Introduction / opening, to what the talk will be about is the title. In Ashdown’s opening, every unit says, in effect, ‘follow me, the meaning is ahead’.

At this point however we need to introduce an important distinction between ‘local’ prospection, where one phrase or sentence leads forward to the next, and ‘longer-range’ prospection where a phrase looks forward to maybe whole topics or themes in driving discourse forward, as in Sinclair’s Janus example: ‘the implications are daunting’ and, here, ‘we live in turbulent times’ which frames the whole talk as crisis diagnosis (‘what kind of turbulence?’ ‘how turbulent?’ ‘why?’ ‘on what evidence?’).

Both of these phrases, Sinclair's and Ashdown's, act as a discourse-opening device that establish an agenda, frame, problem-space, or evaluative horizon whose payoff may unfold over paragraphs, sections, or the whole text/talk.

Ashdown's introduction is a list of 'local' prospective / cataphoric phrases. A workshop would link each one to its following fulfilment (we have included a few CQLs to enable corpora searches for similar constructions):

- 'There's a poem ...' (or perhaps, a 'story', 'song', 'proverb' etc. which authorises narrative as evidence). Which poem? Why mention it?; [word="There" & tag="EX"] [lemma="be"] [word="a|an"] [lemma="story|poem|song|tale|joke"];
- 'it goes like this';
- 'But what Housman understood ...'; CQL [word="What"] [tag="1,4"} [lemma="understand|realise|realize|know|discover"];
- 'And my message for you is ...'; CQL [word="my"] [lemma="message|advice|warning"] [word="for"] [word="you"] [lemma="be"] or perhaps more generally: [word="my"] [tag="N.*"] [word="for"] [word="you"] [lemma="be"].

Cataphora like this, then, is not merely reference delayed; it is discourse momentum engineered.

The second aspect that is impossible not to notice is the speaker's generous use of scaremongering vocabulary: 'soon to die', 'blood', 'bloody', 'terrifying', 'we are condemned'. What on earth are we in for? We are left in no doubt that there is a problem and maybe we are also primed to expect the speaker's solution, which indeed does arrive, though later, after much ado.

And thirdly, the speaker scatters around a number of 'fillers', in this case better described as 'delayers' to deliberately hold back the prospected information in order to help build up the negative tension, indeed leaving *only* the evaluation, such as, 'ladies and gentlemen', 'if you like', 'by the way'.

A follow-up workshop of the similar dark brooding suspense-building use of prospection could begin by concordancing ‘we live in * times’ or using a CQL:

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[word="we|We"] [lemma="live"] [word="in"] [tag="J.*"] [word="times"].
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Concordancing ‘we live in * times’ in the SiBol corpus, reveals a noun group with an overall negative evaluative prosody with a semantic preference for ‘uncertain’, ‘hard - difficult’, ‘testing’, although with the occasional positive describer ‘exciting’ times.

6. Conclusion: From Prospection to Pattern

The analyses presented here have demonstrated that prospection / cataphora and evaluative cohesion are not incidental rhetorical effects, but central organising principles of discourse. Across both the lyrical and political texts examined, forward-oriented signals (‘Had we but...’, ‘Now therefore’, ‘Won't you please forgive me?’ ‘We live in turbulent times...’, ‘Sooner or later...’) function not merely as anticipatory devices, but as structuring mechanisms that guide interpretation over extended stretches of text. In doing so, they create trajectories of expectation which are subsequently confirmed, modulated, or - at times - strategically disrupted, as in the garden-path effect observed in the song ‘Human’.

At the level of close reading, these phenomena are sometimes readily identifiable to a trained discourse analyst. However, without further corroboration, they risk remaining within the domain of interpretive insight. The contribution of corpus linguistics is precisely to extend such observations beyond the individual text, demonstrating that these patterns are not idiosyncratic, but recurrent and systematically distributed across discourse types.

Corpus evidence enables three crucial shifts. First, it allows for pattern generalisation, showing that constructions such as ‘we live in [adj.] times’ or ‘sooner or later’ recur with notable frequency in political discourse, typically preceding evaluative or normative developments. Second, it provides collocational and semantic preference

evidence, revealing that lexical items such as turbulent, challenge, or rule of law participate in conventionalised environments which predispose particular evaluative trajectories. Third, it makes possible register-sensitive comparison, demonstrating that while prospection operates across genres, its scope and density can vary systematically (for example, short-range and immediate evaluative prospection in songs versus extended suspense-building prospection in political speech). Through these shifts, prospection moves from being a descriptive label applied in analysis to a statistically demonstrable tendency of discourse organisation.

This, in turn, invites a broader theoretical integration. If collocation is the visible trace of local co-selection, and evaluative cohesion represents the maintenance of attitudinal consistency across a text, then prospection may be understood as the temporal dimension of co-selection: the projection of likely continuations based on established patterns of use. In this sense, prospection is not an additional layer imposed upon discourse, but an intrinsic property of how discourse unfolds.

Such a view aligns closely with Sinclair's conception of the lexical item as comprising form, meaning, and use. Evaluation, as has long been recognised, straddles meaning and use (Hunston 2013); yet the present analysis suggests that it also operates as a condition of textual well-formedness. Just as a text must achieve propositional coherence to be interpretable, it must also achieve evaluative coherence. Where evaluative expectations are violated without resolution, the result is not merely stylistic markedness but a form of discourse incoherence.

From this perspective, evaluative cohesion emerges as the often-overlooked counterpart to propositional cohesion: a necessary dimension of textual organisation.

Finally, it is worth noting that recent developments in LLMs offer an unexpected form of corroboration for this account. While such models do not encode concepts such as prospection or evaluative cohesion explicitly, their predictive capacities depend on the large-scale modelling of sequential and collocational regularities across vast data collections. Given an initial prompt such as 'We live in turbulent times...', they reliably

generate continuations involving uncertainty, challenge, or change. In doing so, they approximate precisely those forward-oriented co-selection patterns that corpus linguistics has long described.

In this sense, LLMs may be seen as empirically enacting, at scale, a fundamentally Sinclairian insight: that meaning in language arises not only from what has been said, but from what is made expectable. Prospection, evaluative cohesion, and collocational patterning are thus not separate phenomena, but interlocking dimensions of a single underlying principle—namely, that discourse is organised through patterned expectations over time.

Evaluation, then is much more than a recently developed (largely in the field of CL) interesting element in language description. It is a long-missing theoretical dimension of how texts make sense, of how coherence is rendered felicitous to the receiver.

So, as a final word, while the recognition of evaluation at the lexical and phrasal levels — due in no small part to CL and CaDS techniques — may be seen as a genuine ‘rags-to-riches’ development, the role of evaluative cohesion at the textual level remains comparatively under-acknowledged. The present account suggests that it is finally at this level that the pieces fall into place - that the slipper fits - where discourse achieves not only propositional coherence, but evaluative coherence.

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